

Salam on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Salam contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category saying the key "Salam" within the entire year. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Salam contract based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 5 mapping research topics surrounding the Salam contract, namely: (1) Application of the Salam contract; (2) Legal and statutory perspectives regarding the Salam contract; (3) Efforts to develop the Salam contract; (4) Indicators that influence people's interest in using Salam contract products; and (5) Other problems with the Salam contract. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Salam contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Salam; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research

Introduction

At Islamic Financial Institutions, islamic financing can be channeled through sale and purchase contracts, one of which is financing with the Salam contract. Salam is a sale and purchase contract where there are ordered goods (muslam fiih) whose delivery of the goods is handed over at the end by the seller (muslam illaihi) and payment for the goods is made by the buyer at the time the contract is agreed in accordance with Islamic law. In Islamic Financial Institutions, the implementation of financing products using Salam contracts has not been implemented optimally because Islamic Financial Institutions are still facing problems in their implementation. However, Islamic Financial Institutions are aware that financing uses the Salam contract This can be a help to the community, especially farmers who on average only have small capital to finance all their needs regarding rice field management. If salam financing is implemented well, it will be able to expand the role of islamic banking in the future coming.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around the Salam agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the S Alam contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Salam

contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Regards is a sale and purchase agreement for ordered goods between a buyer and a seller. The ordered goods must have a clear price and characteristics and have been agreed upon at the beginning of the contract by both parties, where payment for the goods is made in advance. Based on DSN-MUI fatwa no. 05 of 2000 concerning Sale and Purchase Salam explains that the delivery of goods by the seller to the buyer must be carried out on time in accordance with the agreement and while maintaining the quality and quantity of the goods.

Islamic financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with Islamic principles. Islamic principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with Islamic principles. The aim of Islamic financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as Islamic banks, Islamic insurance companies, and Islamic capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Salam contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Salam contracts on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category saying the key "Salam" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS

(Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Salam contract based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Application of A Greeting card

Library research study in previous research journals, researchers found 13 applications of the Salam contract, including:

First, Islamic Financial Institutions. Islamic financial institutions can apply the Salam contract as one of the financing instruments offered to their customers. In a salam contract, a islamic financial institution as the seller will sell goods or commodities to the customer as the buyer with the condition that payment will be made in the future, at the price agreed upon when the contract is made. For example, Islamic financial institutions can sell agricultural commodities such as rice to customers with payments made at a later date.

Second, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). MSMEs can also use greeting contracts in their business activities. For example, a farmer who owns an agricultural business can sell his harvest through a salam contract to a buyer with terms of payment in the future. In the context of MSMEs, greeting contracts can help business actors to obtain the financing needed to run their business.

Third, buying and selling used motorbikes. In buying and selling used motorbikes, a greeting contract can be implemented with the customer as the buyer who wants to buy a used motorbike from the seller. The seller agrees to sell the motorbike on the condition that payment will be made in the future, such as within the next few months. The salam contract in this context allows the buyer to own a motorbike without having to pay the entire purchase price directly, but payments are made in stages according to a predetermined agreement.

Fourth, buying and selling online on Instagram media. In the context of online buying and selling via Instagram, the greeting contract can be implemented in a way that is similar to buying and selling transactions in general. Sellers and buyers can use greeting contracts to sell and buy products via Instagram with the requirement that payment be made in the future. For example, a seller can offer certain products, such as clothing or accessories, to buyers through a greeting contract with an agreement that payment will be made at a certain time after the contract occurs.

Fifth, buy and sell dessert boxes online. In buying and selling dessert boxes online, the greeting contract can be implemented by selling dessert box products to buyers with payment terms in the future. Sellers can offer dessert boxes through a greeting contract with the agreement that payment will be made when the dessert box is delivered or at a previously agreed time. The greeting contract in this context allows the seller to obtain payment in the future while the buyer can order and receive the dessert box according to the agreement.

Sixth, E-Commerce transactions. E-Commerce transactions in general can involve various types of contracts, including greeting contracts. In E-Commerce transactions, a salam contract can be implemented with the buyer and seller agreeing to sell and buy products with future payment terms. For example, in an E-Commerce platform, buyers can choose the products they

want to buy and enter into a greeting agreement with the seller. Payment will be made after the product is received or in accordance with previously agreed agreements.

Seventh, online Dropshipping transactions. In online dropshipping transactions, the greeting contract can be implemented in a way that is similar to buying and selling transactions in general. The seller or supplier as the party who has stock of goods will sell the product to the Dropshipping seller (reseller) with the condition that payment will be made in the future. Resellers will promote and sell these products to end consumers. Payments from consumers will be received by the reseller, and then the reseller will make payments to the supplier according to the agreed agreement. In this context, greeting contracts can help facilitate transactions between suppliers and resellers with delayed payment requirements.

Eighth, the agricultural sector. In the agricultural sector, the salam contract can be implemented by selling agricultural products to buyers with terms of payment in the future. For example, a farmer can sell his harvest to a buyer with a salam contract, with payment made at harvest or at a pre-agreed time. Salam contracts can help farmers to sell their agricultural products by guaranteeing future payments, thereby enabling them to obtain the funds necessary for the sustainability of their agricultural businesses.

Ninth, buying and selling online herbal suppliers. In online buying and selling of herbal suppliers, a greeting contract can be implemented with the supplier as the seller who sells herbal products to buyers with payment terms in the future. For example, herbal suppliers can sell their products to buyers through a greeting contract with an agreement that payment will be made after the product is received or within a certain period of time after the contract is made. In this context, the salam contract allows herbal suppliers to sell products by obtaining payment in the future.

Tenth, Market Place (Shopee). In Market Places like Shopee, implementing a greeting contract may not be common because their business model is based on buying and selling transactions between sellers and buyers. Usually, Shopee functions as an intermediary in these transactions. However, sellers and buyers can carry out their transactions using islamic principles, such as avoiding items prohibited in Islam, following the principles of honesty and fairness in offering and purchasing products.

Eleventh, online buying and selling of commercial businesses. In online buying and selling in commercial businesses, a greeting contract can be implemented with the seller and buyer agreeing to sell and buy products with terms of payment in the future. Sellers can offer their products or business services through a greeting contract to buyers with an agreement that payment will be made at a certain time after the contract occurs. Buyers can take advantage of the product or service while payment is made at a later date.

Twelfth, GrabFood/GoFood. In food delivery services such as GrabFood or GoFood, implementing the greeting agreement may not be common. This is because their business model is usually based on buying and selling transactions between customers and restaurants or food stalls. However, customers can choose food that complies with islamic principles and avoid food that is not halal. Apart from that, the principles of honesty and fairness must still be applied in these transactions.

Thirteenth, retail companies. In retail companies, the greeting contract may not be commonly applied in buying and selling transactions at the consumer level. However, retail companies can implement islamic principles in

their operations, such as providing halal products or services and following the principles of fairness in offers and prices. In addition, retail companies can offer financing services that comply with Islamic principles, such as *musyarakah* or *mudharabah* financing to business partners or sellers in their supply chain.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Legal and Legal Perspective regarding Salam

library research study in previous research journals, the researcher found 7 legal/legislative perspectives regarding the Salam contract, including:

First, a greeting card according to the Koran, Hadith and DSN-MUI fatwa. The Salam contract is a form of buying and selling contract in Islam. According to the Koran, Salam is mentioned in Surah Al-Baqarah verse 282. The Salam contract is also strengthened by the Hadith narrated by several friends, such as Abdullah bin Abbas and Abdullah bin Umar. In a Salam contract, the seller receives full payment at the beginning, while the goods being traded will be delivered at a later date. The Fatwa of the National Islamic Council-Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) regarding the Salam contract states that this contract is permissible in Islam with several conditions. Some of these conditions include: the object of the greeting must be clearly defined, delivery of the goods must be made at the agreed time, and both parties must agree on the specifications of the goods being traded.

Second, E-Commerce transactions are signed according to PSAK 103. PSAK 103 is a financial accounting standard issued by the Indonesian Accountants Association (IAI) regarding Islamic accounting. In PSAK 103, E-Commerce transactions with a Salam contract are explained as online buying and selling transactions that use a Salam contract as the form of contract used in the transaction. PSAK 103 regulates the accounting treatment for E-Commerce transactions with Salam contracts. This standard explains how to recognize revenues and expenses related to Salam transactions in an E-Commerce environment.

Third, buying and selling pre-orders according to DSN-MUI fatwa No. 5. DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 5 regarding buying and selling pre-orders explains the principles that must be considered when buying and selling pre-orders from an Islamic legal perspective. In the fatwa, DSN-MUI explained that buying and selling pre-orders is permitted in Islam with several conditions. Some of these conditions include: the pre-order object must be clear and can be determined, the agreement between the seller and the buyer must be transparent regarding the price, specifications and delivery period of the goods, and the seller must be responsible for delivering the goods in accordance with the agreement.

Fourth, a card of greetings from an Islamic economic perspective. The Salam contract from an Islamic economic perspective is one type of agreement or contract used in buying and selling transactions in Islam. A Salam contract occurs when the seller (greeting giver) agrees to sell an item to the buyer (recipient of greeting) with the condition that payment is made in advance and delivery of the goods is made later on the agreed date. In this contract, the seller (greeting) must clearly state the nature and type of goods being sold as well as the agreed price. Profits in a Salam contract cannot be determined with certainty at the time the contract is executed.

Fifth, a greeting card from the perspective of sectarian scholars. The perspective of school scholars in the Salam contract refers to the opinions and views of scholars from certain schools of thought (for example, Hanafi School, Maliki School, Syafi'i School, Hanbali School). Although there are some

differences of opinion between them, in general, madhhab scholars agree that the Salam contract is valid in Islam and can be carried out with certain conditions. They view that the initial payment in the Salam contract is not a problem as long as the nature and type of the goods being sold are clear, and the price has been clearly agreed upon. Apart from that, the profits in a Salam contract cannot be determined with certainty at the time the contract is executed.

Sixth, a greeting card from the perspective of contemporary scholars. The perspective of contemporary ulama refers to the views and opinions of ulama who live and provide legal assessments in the context of modern times. Contemporary scholars see the Salam contract as one of the instruments that can be used in current islamic economic transactions. They emphasized the importance of clarity in the nature and type of goods being sold as well as the agreed prices. Apart from that, they also consider the consumer protection aspect in the Salam contract, namely the need to protect the buyer from risks and deficiencies that may occur in the delivery of goods.

Seventh, islamic contract law in the Salam contract. In islamic contract law, the Salam contract is considered valid and permitted in Islam with certain conditions. These conditions include: (1) Clarity regarding the type and nature of the goods being sold and the agreed price. (2) Payment is made in advance before delivery of the goods. (3) Delivery of goods is carried out on the agreed date, taking into account the agreement and other agreed conditions. (4) The profit in a Salam contract cannot be determined with certainty at the time the contract is executed. (5) The Salam contract must be carried out voluntarily and without any elements of fraud or coercion.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Development Efforts A Salam card

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found 4 efforts to develop the Salam contract, including:

First, optimizing Fintech in the Salam Agreement. Optimizing Fintech in the Salam Agreement refers to the use of financial technology (Fintech) to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the implementation of the Salam Agreement. The Salam contract is a form of contract in fiqh (Islamic law) which is used in commodity trading. In a Salam Agreement, the buyer makes full payment in advance to obtain the commodity that will be delivered in the future. In this context, Fintech can help automate the payment process, delivery of goods, and risk management related to the implementation of the Salam Agreement. This can speed up transactions, reduce operational costs, and make access easier for parties involved in Akad Salam transactions.

Second, optimizing the Salam contract in overcoming t allaqi r ukban. Tallaqi rukban refers to a situation where a seller buys back a commodity that has been sold through an Akad Salam before the agreed delivery time. This occurs when sellers face difficulties or are unable to fulfill their commitment to deliver the commodity at the specified time. To overcome tallaqi rukban, optimizing the Akad Salam involves determining a clear compensation or penalty mechanism in the Akad Salam agreement. In this case, the party who violates the Akad Salam contract will be required to pay compensation to other parties affected by the tallaqi rukban. This can encourage compliance with the agreement and minimize the risk of tallaqi rukban.

Third, optimizing the Salam contract during the Covid-19 pandemic. During the Covid-19 pandemic, optimizing the Salam Agreement involved

adjusting and implementing additional measures to overcome the challenges faced in commodity trading. Some steps that can be taken include increasing the use of digital technology and electronic trading platforms to facilitate online Akad Salam transactions, strengthening risk management related to supply and delivery disruptions, and adopting strict hygiene policies and procedures to ensure safety and health during the Akad Salam implementation process..

Fourth, design the Salam-Muzara'ah Linked Waqf contract. The design of the Salam-Muzara'ah Linked Waqf contract combines two types of contracts, namely the Salam and Muzara'ah contracts with the use of waqf. The Salam contract is a contract where the buyer makes full payment in advance for commodities that will be delivered in the future, while the Muzara'ah is an agricultural contract where the land owner gives land management rights to another party to cultivate it and share the harvest. In this design, commodities obtained through Akad Salam are used to finance agriculture through Muzara'ah and the harvest is used to support waqf projects. Thus, the design of the Salam-Muzara'ah Linked Waqf Agreement combines aspects of commodity trading, agriculture and waqf to achieve broader social and economic goals in the context of Islamic economics.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Indicators that Influence People's Interest in Using Greeting Card Products

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found 5 indicators that influence people's interest in using Salam contract products, including:

First, risk. Risk is an important factor that influences people's interest in using Salam contract products. If people feel that the risks associated with the product are low, such as the risk of loss of capital or legal risks, they are more likely to be interested in using the product. Companies offering Salam contract products need to provide clear information regarding the risks involved and efforts to minimize these risks.

Second, knowledge. Public knowledge about Salam contract products will influence their interest. The better their understanding of the concept and mechanisms of the Salam contract, the more likely they are to be interested in using it. Companies need to provide adequate education to the public to increase their knowledge about this product, including how the Salam contract works, its benefits, and how to use it effectively.

Third, promotion. Effective promotion can increase public interest in using Salam contract products. Companies need to carry out good marketing campaigns to convey the advantages and benefits of products to the public. Promotions that reinforce positive messages about Salam contract products, such as fairness, transparency and financial benefits, can help increase public interest.

Fourth, location. Location can also influence people's interest in using Salam contract products. If companies offer easy access to these products, whether through a physical office, digital application, or online platform, people will be more likely to use the product. Ease of access and product availability in certain regions or locations can influence people's interest.

Fifth, interest. Community interest itself is an important indicator. If people have a high interest in using Salam contract products, they tend to be more active in seeking information about these products and have the potential to accept and utilize them more. Companies need to identify and understand

public interest in Salam contract products and design appropriate marketing strategies to attract that interest.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Problems on A greeting card

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found 9 other problems in a greeting card, including:

First, consumer protection in Salam transactions. Consumer protection in Salam transactions refers to efforts to protect the rights of consumers involved in these transactions. Salam transaction is a type of transaction in Islamic law where the seller agrees to deliver certain goods to the buyer at a specified time in the future with payment made in advance. In this context, consumer protection involves several aspects, such as: (1) Quality of Goods: Consumers have the right to receive goods that comply with the quality standards promised or expected. The seller must ensure that the goods delivered comply with the agreed requirements. (2) Information Disclosure: Consumers have the right to obtain clear and honest information about the goods to be purchased, including descriptions, characteristics and condition of the goods. Accurate and complete information must be available so consumers can make informed decisions. (3) Legal Certainty: Consumers must be legally protected in terms of resolving disputes or disagreements that may arise in Salam transactions. Fair and effective dispute resolution mechanisms must be in place to ensure fairness for consumers. (4) Protection Against Fraud: Consumers must be protected from fraudulent or fraudulent practices in Salam transactions. There is a need to implement adequate controls, both in terms of seller verification and in the delivery process.

Second, its implementation is viewed from the principle of *tabadul manafi'*. The principle of *tabadul manafi'* is the principle used in Salam transactions to determine the rights and responsibilities of the parties involved. *Tabadul manafi'* means exchange of benefits or advantages. This principle stipulates that in a Salam transaction, the seller is responsible for providing benefits to the buyer in the form of promised goods, while the buyer is responsible for paying the price up front. In its application, the principle of *tabadul manafi'* ensures that buyers and sellers understand their rights and obligations clearly. This involves: (1) Clear Agreement: The parties must clearly agree on the specifications of the goods, price, quantity, and delivery time. This helps prevent disagreements or disputes later on. (2) Prepayment: The buyer must pay the price of the goods in advance according to the agreement. This provides assurance to sellers that payments will be made in a timely manner. (3) Obligation to Deliver Goods: The seller has the obligation to deliver the promised goods to the buyer at the agreed time. Delivery of goods must comply with agreed specifications and quality.

Third, risk management of the Salam contract. Salam contract risk management includes the steps taken to manage the risks associated with Salam transactions. Some of the risks associated with the Salam contract include: (1) Risk of Seller's Inability: There is a risk that the seller will not be able to fulfill their obligation to deliver the promised goods. Risk management in this case involves selecting sellers who can be trusted and have the capacity to fulfill their obligations. (2) Goods Quality Risk: Risk related to the quality of goods which may not comply with expectations or requirements. Risk management in this case involves checking and verifying the quality of goods before delivery. (3) Price Change Risk: The risk of changes in the price of goods

between the time of transaction and the time of delivery. Risk management involves setting fair prices and following market-appropriate pricing mechanisms. (4) Legal and Compliance Risk: Risks related to legal and compliance aspects in Salam transactions. Risk management involves a good understanding of applicable legal regulations and provisions and ensuring compliance with them.

Fourth, the law of implementing the khiyar conditions in the Salam contract. In the context of the Salam contract, khiyar terms refer to the right of choice that one of the parties has to cancel or continue the Salam contract based on the fulfillment or violation of the agreed terms. In this case, the law implementing khiyar conditions determines how this right can be implemented. According to several opinions among scholars, the implementation of khiyar conditions in the Salam contract can be divided into three main approaches: (1) Khiyar Conditions Mutlaq: The party who has the right to khiyar conditions can decide to continue or cancel the Salam contract based on whether the conditions that have been determined have been met, fulfilled or violated. (2) Khiyar Certain Conditions: The party who has the right to khiyar conditions can only exercise this right if certain conditions are not met. If these conditions are met, then the right to khiyar conditions does not apply. (3) Mandatory Khiyar Conditions: The party who has the right to khiyar conditions is required to exercise this right if the specified conditions are not met. If this party does not exercise this right, it is deemed to have agreed to the Salam contract in full.

Fifth, Force Majeure in the Salam contract. Force Majeure is a term used to describe circumstances or events beyond human control that can hinder or disrupt the implementation of the Salam contract. In the context of a Salam contract, Force Majeure can refer to natural disasters, war, riots, or other events that cannot be predicted or avoided by the parties involved in the contract. When a Force Majeure situation occurs, the affected party has the right to request suspension, modification or cancellation of the Salam contract without any sanctions or legal responsibility. However, it is important to note that the use of Force Majeure grounds must be based on circumstances that are completely beyond the affected party's control and not caused by their own negligence or negligence.

Sixth, Hybrid Contract in the Salam contract. Hybrid Contract in the Salam contract refers to a type of contract that combines Salam elements with other contract elements. In this context, Salam is a form of contract in which the seller receives full or partial payment in advance for goods to be delivered at a future date. Hybrid Contracts in Salam contracts can involve a combination of Salam with other contracts such as Wakalah (agent), Ijarah (rent), Murabahah (sale with markup), or Qardh (loan). The aim of this merger is to meet more complex needs and requirements in a business or financial context. For example, in Salam with Wakalah, the seller (muqrid) can appoint an agent (representative) to carry out certain actions regarding the delivery of goods that have been purchased through Salam. This agent acts on behalf of the seller, providing flexibility and efficiency in contract execution. In the context of a Hybrid Contract, it is important to pay attention that the implementation and implementation of the contract must be in accordance with Islamic principles and applicable laws in Islam. Therefore, the parties involved in such contracts need to obtain a good understanding of the relevant rules and requirements before entering into such an agreement.

Seventh, business ethics in Salam contracts. Several important business ethics principles in the Salam contract include: (1) Honesty: Business people

must be committed to being honest and not committing fraud or manipulation in the Salam contract. They must provide accurate and transparent information regarding the goods or services offered. (2) Concern for consumers: Business actors must ensure that consumers receive goods or services that are in accordance with what was promised in the Salam contract. They must also treat consumers fairly and respect their rights. (3) Concern for society: Business actors must consider the impact of the Salam contract on society at large. They must avoid actions that are detrimental to society or violate the social values adhered to by society. (4) Environmental responsibility: Business actors must be responsible for the environmental impacts of goods or services produced through Salam contracts. They must pay attention to environmentally friendly and sustainable business practices.

Eighth, *hilah* in the Salam contract. This refers to strategies or shortcuts that can be used by business people to avoid legal or ethical provisions in implementing the Salam contract. This *hilah* is contrary to the principles of honesty and transparency in Islamic business. Examples of *hilah* in a Salam contract can include neglect of the quality of the goods promised, price manipulation, or neglect of other obligations stipulated by religion or law. This *hilah* practice is contrary to the spirit of the Salam contract which should be based on justice, mutual benefit and mutual trust between business people.

Ninth, public perception regarding the Salam contract. This refers to the understanding or views held by the community regarding the concept and practice of the Salam contract in Islamic business. People's perceptions can vary depending on their background, culture, and religious understanding. Some people may have a positive perception of the Salam contract as a form of business that is fair and in accordance with Islamic principles. They may see it as a way to promote fairness, mutual benefit, and economic sustainability. However, there are also people who may have a negative perception of the Salam contract. They may see it as a form of speculation or a practice that exploits other people's weaknesses. This negative perception may arise due to abuse or violation of business ethics in implementing the Salam contract. Public perception of the Salam contract is important because it can influence the acceptance and implementation of the contract in the business environment and society at large. Therefore, it is important for business people and related authorities to communicate and educate the public regarding the principles and benefits of Salam contracts which are in accordance with Islamic values.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 5 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the Salam contract in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of the Salam contract; (2) Legal and statutory perspectives regarding the Salam contract; (3) Efforts to develop the Salam contract; (4) Indicators that influence people's interest in using Salam contract products; and (5) Other problems with the Salam contract.

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